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Pritilata Ojha

Former Student,
Dept. of Geography,
University of Calcutta,
West Bengal, India

Correspondence:**Pritilata Ojha**

Former Student,
Dept. of Geography,
University of Calcutta,
West Bengal, India

Development in Geographical Thought

Pritilata Ojha

Abstract:

Development of geographical thought was oriented to, from origination of universe to present critical reality study. It mainly covered by Pre-Greeko-Roman era to present day. Pre-Greeko-Roman era was the beginning of human being, human-civilization, and the birth place of knowledge budding of language, agriculture, fire discovery, wheel discovery. For their surviving they created navigation system, travelling, expand their culture and barter practice is a mode of communication between many civilizations, these expand geographical knowledge because that is the study of earth, and earth related things are geographic knowledge. So, observation, story writing, astronomical study, physical geography study, these are the study of earth, earth and celestial body relationship, about ocean, tide, currents is the part of ancient study. In medieval period geographical study mainly oriented three countries, such as India, China and Arabian countries. Mathematics, astronomy and physical geography is the central point of geographical study. In this era, Mainly Arabians were travelling many places mainly eastern country like India, China and harvesting knowledge from their existing mythology and contemporaneous innovation. And Arabians were accumulate these knowledge and stored in book. They are research many existing knowledge of strabo and ptolemy, independently they innovate many idea climate, geomorphology etc. Then later middle age is the time of exploration and discovery of many unknown world. In modern era many observation based geographical tools like Altimeter used by Humboldt, empirical study, then present day's analytical scientific study, GPS system, spatial geography depend on totally scientific exploration and relativity to contemporary world. Ptolemy's map making, determination of direction, projection system and Eratosthenes measurements of earth perimeter. Thales and Anaximander's mathematical astronomical discovery like Gnomon instruments innovation which is used for time, date, solstice and equinox. Seismometer by China, invention of zero, gravitation laws etc. in Indian mythology. So the ancient era's geographical tools and instruments was the base of contemporary scientific study. These are based on recent new innovation and now a days applied geography is solving many environment related problem and create clear view for many purpose, exp-economic activities in restricted areas like mining in mountain area because many scientific analysis accumulate and create geographical study. Study areas in soil, ground water, agriculture, climate- as create artificial train, vegetation study for Ayurveda, all these are include in areal study as well as geographical level of image of this area. So geographical study now a days is more relevance than other subject. Mother Earth is the habitat place for all organism, so we are all responsible for protection of our earth. So, when our inquisitiveness is any earth related issues then our thinking answer these issues and more flourished our earth science as geography.

Keywords - Understanding about present context of Geographical study, Geographical thought related inquisitiveness development in student mind, Knowing about geography Subject's development budding to blossoming.

Introduction:

In geography, the geographical thought gave a chronological sequence of many approaches, these are the main pillar of geographical Studies. And this sequential studies

were well explained by Kuhn's Paradigm approach. But this paradigm approach not proper representation of development of geographical thought because one approach of geography is different from other approach but interrelated i.e. basis of one approach to others. So we don't draw a Clear cut line between two/ three approach in geography and some approaches are overlapping each other.

Exp – Positivism Approach + Humanistic Approach = Post positivism Approach

So, here quantitative and qualitative approach are mingled.

The development of approaches in geography are as a sequence generally as →Encyclopedia → Empiricism → Determinism → Possibilism → Regional Approach → Systematic Approach → Theory, Model and Hypothesis → System Approach → Concept of Space → Concept of Time → Realism → Behaviouralistic approach → Radical geography → Humanistic Approach → Feminist approach → Welfare approach → Fordism → Structuralism→Modernism → Post-Modernism → Environment approach → Applied geography.

But these approaches in geographical studies create different studies and they align together solve many geographical problems mostly now a days known as applied geography. And these approach not in a one day's one geographer's view. These approaches were originated year to year perseverance, study and philosophical Superiority of geographer's view and controversy in their doctrines create newer approach. Even many geographers are contributed in many way in development of one approach of geographical thinking.

And also the geographical approaches are developed in many era and many country's contribution. Ancient time - Greek (Description, observation, mathematical, Astronomical study, literary study) & Roman (Historical and Regional geography, field of physical and mathematical geography).

Medieval time (Dark Age in Europe and contributions of Muslims, Indians and Chinese). Then the late medieval time (Voyage and discovery of European country).

The Modern era (we don't divide country only one approach, one country contribute development of many approach but there was a main focus in views, As such - German (Deterministic Approach), France (Possibility Approach), British (Regional approach), American (Deterministic, quantitative method), Russian (Deterministic and Marxist approach).

So many geographer, traveller, poet, historian, mathematician, were left behind many important contribution development of many idea, thought in geography.

OBJECTIVES:

Main objective as the title suggests, is to understand the revolution in geographical thought. Geographical imaginations, inquisitiveness and geographical enquiry

create new innovation in thought, observation process, discovery of new places and shifting geographical studies to doctrine.

This type of change in thought is quite shapely explained in concept of paradigm shift as crisis phase and paradigm phase. Such as one or "a set of philosophies with sufficient commonality of focus and approach and a large group of practitioners may constitute a paradigm" - (Harvey & Holly, 1989).

Initiation of a new paradigm, the scientific study created related to new paradigm. In this way knowledge is increasing and new paradigm became conventional paradigm then criticized by new questioning, new problem in this way is not possible to tackle the present crisis that's way creates a chaos and a revolutionary phase, then accept a new idea that resolve the present crisis and answering the questions or inquisitiveness in research gap. In this way new paradigm flourished. And only paradigm is not an answer for development of geographical thought. Because not only one paradigm or accumulation of one more idea help us in geographical study or goodwill for human being but many root ideas, many thought which has a paradigm type nature and they are interrelated, there are accumulation of previous many paradigm proved approaches. Because we know that 'Modernism' is a paradigm's proved approach now a days more precisely that is "Post modernism" which accumulate modernism + different human culture or context (human approach).

So this reflect the two paradigm's proved ideas accumulation.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Development of geographical thought in geography create a basic sense about the origination of geography subject and modifications of different approaches different times with the context of present requirements.

Beginning of concept of geography is mainly based on write prose / poems about place, observation and description of facts, inductive and deductive study of events but before that knowledge is central to civilization, like as Indus Valley civilization, Vedic civilization, Egyptian civilization, Mesopotamian civilization and the world's oldest writing system (cuneiform) developed by Sumerians in Mesopotamia (modern Iraq) before 3200 BC. The Phoenician alphabet was one of the first widespread phonetic scripts, where each of the 22 symbols represented a consonant sound, thereafter added vowel with it and Phoenicians are prominently residents of eastern part of Mediterranean and advanced in navigation and so they expand their knowledge progressively.

Then the fall of Roman Empire and crusades era, dark age in Europe (AD 200 - AD 700) because the geographical study, place exploration, description of place, scientific study should be quietly in paused in Christian Europe but at this time the geographical study via mathematics,

trigonometry, astronomy science, observation and narratives, folklore are the method of geographical study in India, China and Arabs. After the Mohammad, the Caliphate were enthusiastic in collection of knowledge and expand empire because they are understand that travelling is the key tool to expand the knowledge and religion for development of Islamic civilization. They are travel mainly in eastern country (Indian subcontinent and China). In India and China the geographical study was oriented to astronomy, map making, physical geography and flourished itself. So we are assumed that eastern knowledge is expand by the traveller to the middle east and western and knowledge are protected in western library of Miletus (ancient) and library of Alexandria, after European exploration of Alexander then knowledge back to the eastern country. Arabian traveler accumulate knowledge create experiment and stored in book and translate many book in Arabian language then these books are deciphered in Latin, Greek and later medieval era mainly coastal country of Europe started navigation for new place exploration (1400-1700 AD). Christopher Columbus discovered new country America (1492) and other explorer are Chou-Ta-Kuan, Bartolomeu Dias, Vasco da gama, Ferdinand Magellan, and James cook. So the ancient and medieval era were the **Encyclopedic phase** Then many colonies are formed in many country and after that many social change these colonies are erased by independence. After that modern period was started with the enlightenment of Renaissance scientific knowledge and analysis are prioritized, and the observation, exploration with empirical study and generalization, specialization, uses of instruments and tools to measure height, temperature, pressure etc., i.e. observable things and empirical study on many spots (mountain, river, ocean currents). Starting phase of modern era a **Empiricism phase & Teleological** concepts many times wanted to prove that all things are cause of nature as well as inquisitiveness in geographer's mind creates many new idea and trying to denial the teleological concept. Question → Perception → Concept → Theory → Paradigm.

The paradigm represents dominance of nature. **Deterministic** approach represents dominance of nature on human being. **Possibilism** give more power on human being. **Systematic** approach means one things distributes how many places of the world and **regional** approach is in one place, all things are distributed which pattern. Quantitative study is the base of theory, hypothesis, model and law, Hypothesis testing on existing **theory** it represents existing theory accepted or rejected like null or alternative hypothesis, **Hypothesis** testing on continental drift theory, then it is accepted. **Model** is the generalized, easy and ideal representation of real world. System

approach explains many agents of the system and relation between them.

Spatial organization explain pattern and process of phenomena, It is express the form, nature and cause of the areal differentiation or variation on the surface of the Earth and the **time** also a concept which explain chronological diversity of phenomena.

Realism - The primary knowledge about material is the science, that knowledge given concept about material's structure and characteristics, this knowledge of matter formed by general rule.

Behaviouralism:

Interaction between man and environment and human being change environment according to their intellectual and mental satisfaction and also changed by environmental circumstances.

Radicalism:

The concept which creates radical change in social and economic structure of society creates peaceful, structured social system.

Humanistic Approach:

Feeling, intellectuality and cognitive status of human being creates different circumstances and study of human oriented approach is known as humanistic approach.

Feminist Approach:

The study of gender disparity and creates equality in gender and opportunity of employment for woman.

Welfare Approach:

The study of poverty, starvation, criminality, castism, education and wealth in which trying to create equality and eradication of poverty, starvation etc. "Welfare geography is who gets what, where and how?"

(D. M. Smith, 1977)

Fordism:

In this phase worldwide development and excessive indulgence creates social and regional disparity. Industrialization and factory, real estate creates radical change in society and owner-labour good-relationship, labour classification creates labour disparity, gender disparity, exploitation of natural resource emerged poverty and deterioration of social system.

Structuralism:

The study of any events or activity or landscape's. Outer structure is created by many internal activity, principle, logic or multilayered things are interrelated and create a structure. E.g. Communism destroy capitalism and land of free from industrial society.

Modernism:

The state of good, updated, developed, superior lifestyle, social system in any time span which is naturally mean European society after industrial revolution.

Post-Modernism:

Could relate social aspect of human with modernism. Then Environment protectionism and after that many applied geographical approach is formulated for real world problem solving.

So when we are seen the paradigm approach or sequence of geographical approach but not fully reflect the geographical approach development because Paradigm escape many other prominent doctrine of geography. Such as political geography is partly of determinism not completely. Biogeography not a part of anyone paradigm. New determinism also a impactful concept in geography which trying to balance between determinism and possibilism but not a part of anyone paradigm concept.

Industrial geography also a part of quantitative, capitalistic, Fordism and radical approach. And economic theory, model also a part of deterministic, empirical and a systematic approach and now a day's environment, applied geography are also aggregate of many idea, perception and thought.

So paradigm approach just a formality not a reality. Even in paradigm shift "The duck-rabbit optical illusion" made to demonstrate the way in which a paradigm shift could cause one to see the same information in an entirely different way.

(Kuhn & Wittgenstein)

Ptolemy's geocentric model of universe.

Copernicus heliocentric astronomy.

Now a days Centre of universe not sun, not earth...this is now in the area of scientific study.

METHODS:

The purpose of this study is to know about the developmental phase, important approach and nature of subject i.e. it is interdisciplinary in nature to know the subject's core area that is primarily in descriptive and qualitative nature then it is quantitative based mixed method/approach. This research article is lead to Thematic Analysis (T.A) method. Reviewed some existing research method, generating initial code, points the clarify relation between geographic terminology, event, fact, concept then written up.

Citation Style took APA style.

RESULTS:

The development of geographical thought was a revolutionary process when there were many thought but which thought is more suitable to present scenario that is exist. And that is fulfill the present knowledge crisis and this thought create a umbrella type framework where many idea support one paradigm.

Exp- The determinism approach is a aggregate of many approach such as Darwin's survival of fittest, Davis's normal cycle of erosion is a systematic approach, Fredrick Ratzel's Anthropogeography, Sample's Environmental Determinism, Huntington's climatic determinism such an example etc. Then this deterministic approach face a

questioning about robustness of nature and inferiority of human conception.

This questioning make a perception then conception there after a new paradigm possibilism was a place of deterministic approach.

So the development history teaches us in any purpose of geographical study, geographical imaginations, inquisitiveness and geographical enquiry, analysis create crisis, then new innovation is flourished and new thought is came fulfill the crisis phase. Inductive & deductive approach of Aristotle & Plato, learned us how we propagate new theory and law. And we don't fully aware about geography from beginning to present state with only studied by paradigm because in early stage geography was observation, story making and exploration, mathematical, astronomical and analysis based. In differentiation of study we couldn't them take under one umbrella frame, so we are also studied about in different era's, different geographer's contribution and they generate many idea, explore thought in which process and made many idea fulfill the demand of contemporary world.

So we are learned from this, if basic idea of geography in student mind, so we create many innovative idea in our mind through many inquisitiveness(why earthquake, flood, origin of universe, EIA, plant study, zoo geography, climatic variation, social problem related theory etc). And geography is more flourished better than other subject if it is not that will be create existential crisis in geography subject. Because in dark age (1200 AD) our geography subject cancelled from education system i.e. university, college and school for 1000 year, because geography related research, analysis, exploration, information gather stop in europe, it was a mother of science which means interdisciplinary in nature integrates knowledge from multiple disciplines, cross domain, multi perspective. So, applicability create relevancy of subject.

CONCLUSION:

The evolution of geographical thought represent discipline's ability to fill up crisis phase, creates intellectually many idea which adapt in the era of technologically advancements and societal concerns i.e. solving many environmental issue. From ancient observation and Philosophical reflection to modern scientific research, geography has created many branch of science - Climatology, Bio-geography, cultural geography, oceanography, environmental geography, GIS, Remote sensing, Statistical geography etc. This subject's versatility and broader sense of area not only contribute by geographer in different studies also other social science, natural science subject's expert contribute to generate many idea, analysis in field of geography is create importance of subject in addresses key challenge such as climate change, urban development, social inequality, application of geo-spatial technology and unsolved

environmental problem. Now a day's geographical knowledge about local and global issue is more relevant in expanding ICT, sustainable concept, regional planning, multipurpose project, because in these purpose geographical tools and analysis are required, so in these field, now a days applied geography playing great role in these field. So, geography not a natural science but mother of science which is the birth field of many natural science so we don't ever underestimate geography's relevancy recent world.

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